

ELECTROMAGNETIC WAVE ABSORBING PROPERTIES OF CO NANO POWDER AND CARBON NANO-FIBERS EMBEDDED COMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

In recent years, the electromagnetic interference (EMI) problem has become more serious due to wide applications of high frequency electromagnetic (EM) waves (higher than 1 GHz) into commercial and military fields such as mobile phone, local area network, radar system, military equipments and so on. Much effort has been devoted to the development of better EM absorbing material using dielectric or (and) magnetic lossy materials. Generally, EM wave absorption properties of materials depend on their dielectric (permittivity), magnetic properties (permeability), thickness and frequency [1-2].

In general, dielectric and magnetic EM wave absorbers have their own pros and cons. Dielectric absorbers consisting of only dielectric lossy materials such as carbon nanofiber (CNFs), and multi-walled carbon nanotube (MWNTs) require heavy impedance matching thickness and narrow absorbing bandwidths (BWs) [3]. On the other hand, magnetic absorbers employing only metallic or ferromagnetic materials have thin thickness and broad absorbing BWs. However, it has some disadvantages such as heavy weight, poor properties in high frequency because of Snoek limit [4].

This study presents EM wave absorbers with light, thin and high performance. Optimum lossy materials were selected and then EM wave absorbers were prepared by hybridization of both dielectric and magnetic lossy materials. It was reported that complex permittivity of CNFs is higher than other carbon nano materials and Cobalt (Co) is better magnetic properties (permeability and magnetizing force) than other ferromagnetic substances such as

Iron (Fe) and Nickel (Ni) in high frequency range [3-4]. So, CNFs and Co nanopowders [Co_(p)] were selected as dielectric and magnetic lossy materials, and prepared by hybridizing them. This paper addresses the preparation of EM wave absorbers, measurement of complex permittivities in the range of 0.5~18 GHz, design of single-layered X-band (8.2~12.4 GHz) EM wave absorbers and performance evaluation of several selected specimens.

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials

Co_(p) (Solgo Nanoadvance, Korea) with 700 nm of powder diameter were made by pulsed wire evaporation method. Also, the vapor-grown CNF (VGCF-H, Showa Denko, Japan), Bisphenol A type epoxy resin (YD-128, Kukdo Chemical, Korea), anhydride type hardner (KBH-1089, Kukdo Chemical, Korea) were used as dielectric lossy material, matrix of EM wave absorber, respectively. All ingredients were used as received.

2.2 The fabrication of EM wave absorbers

Six kinds of EM wave absorbers embedding Co_(p) and CNFs were prepared by processes in shown Fig. 1. First of all, the epoxy resin, lossy materials and hardner was pre-mixed by mechanical stirrer under 500 rpm for 10 min and the lossy materials were sufficiently dispersed into the resin using a three roll mill (80E, EXAKT, Germany). Then, the mixture was degassed in vacuum oven at 80 °C. After that, degassed mixture was cured for 3 hrs at 120 °C.

Fig.1. Schematic diagram of preparation of EM wave absorber containing $\text{Co}_{(p)}$ and CNFs.

2.3 Characterization

SEM (JEOL-5800, JEOL, Japan) was used to observe the dispersity of fillers in matrix and the microstructure of EM wave absorber. Scatter parameters (S-parameters) were measured by vector network analyzer (VNA, Agilent N5230A) and 7 mm coaxial airline to obtain complex permittivity and permeability of EM wave absorbers. The complex permittivity and permeability were calculated from S-parameters using 85071E (Material Measurement Software) from 0.5 GHz to 18.0 GHz [5].

3 Results and discussion

The dispersity, the aspect ratio and the concentration of fillers have effect on EM property of composites and performance of the absorbers. In order to optimize fabrication process and design ultra-thin EM wave absorber, this research carried out several preparation of the composites by different mixing process and concentration of CNFs in shown Table 1. Complex permittivity and permeability of the composites are measured and discussed.

Table 1. Recipe for several EM wave absorbers

Sample No/	Conc. of $\text{Co}_{(p)}$ (wt%)	Conc. of CNFs (wt%)	Roll gap ($\mu\text{m}/\mu\text{m}$)	Number of cycles
HEM-1	50	1.5	5/5	4
HEM-2	50	1.5	10/10	4
HEM-3	50	1.5	10/10	5
HEM-4	50	1.5	10/10	7
HEM-5	50	1.0	10/10	4
HEM-6	50	2.0	10/10	4

3.1 The optimization of fabrication process

3.1.1 Effect of roll gap

Two different roll gap in the three roll mill were used to investigate the influence of the mixing process on the EM property of composites.

Fig. 2 shows microstructure of specimens. CNFs and $\text{Co}_{(p)}$ are well dispersed in matrix and, in addition, there is almost no porosity.

Fig. 3 shows real and imaginary part of complex permittivity and permeability of two different EM wave absorbers. While the permeability shows no variation in the two processes, the complex permittivity increases according to the roll gap. This result indicates that increased shear force between rolls in the decreased roll gap leads the fracture of CNFs.

Fig.2. SEM micrographs of EM wave absorbers prepared by different roll gap in mixing process ; (a) : HEM-1, (b) : HEM-2

Fig.3. Permittivity and permeability of composites prepared by different roll gap in mixing process

3.1.2 Effect of repetition

Fig. 4 is SEM micrographs of cross-section area of specimens prepared by three different numbers of repetition in mixing process. $Co_{(p)}$ and CNFs are dispersed well in matrix. Fig. 5 presents the complex permittivity and permeability of composites prepared by different number of repetition in mixing process. The complex permeability do not changes so much in this comparison but the complex permittivity is decreasing as the number of repetition increases. This result shows that increase of repetition has effect on EM property of composite. Therefore, it needs to optimize the mixing process by controlling of roll gap and number of repetition.

Fig. 4. SEM images of EM wave absorbers prepared by different number of repetition in mixing process; (a) : HEM-2, (b) : HEM-3, (d) : HEM-4

Fig. 5. Permittivity and permeability of composites prepared by different number of repetition in mixing process

3.2 Effect of concentration of CNFs

Fig. 6 shows SEM micrographs of microstructure of composites with three different concentrations of CNFs. In all composites, $Co_{(p)}$ and CNFs are dispersed well in matrix and there's nearly no micropore. Fig. 7 presents complex permittivity and permeability of the composites. It must be noted the complex permeability does not vary so much in all composite. However, complex permittivity increases in proportional to the concentration of CNF.

Fig. 6. SEM images of composites with three different concentration of CNFs; (a) : HEM-5, (b) : HEM-2, (d) : HEM-6

Fig. 7. Permittivity and permeability of composites with three concentrations of CNFs

3.3 EM wave absorber design

The governing equation of single-layer absorber is a simple case of the transmission line method. Fig. 8 shows the schematic drawing of single-layer absorber. Permittivity (ϵ) and permeability (μ) can

be obtained from Eq. (1). In Eq. (1), where c is the speed of light in air.

$$\tanh\left(\frac{j2\pi f d}{c} \sqrt{\mu_r \epsilon_r}\right) = \sqrt{\frac{\epsilon_r}{\mu_r}} \quad (1)$$

When complex permeability ($\mu_r = \mu' - j\mu''$) is fixed in all composites at frequency (f) of 10 GHz, the complex permittivity ($\epsilon_r = \epsilon' - j\epsilon''$) can be obtained for every prescribed thickness (d).

Fig. 8. Schematic drawing of the single-layer absorber

Fig. 9 shows Cole-Cole plot (the real part of complex values on x -axis the imaginary part on y -axis) of complex permittivity. The plot is composed with two curves including the solutions ($\epsilon_r = \epsilon' - j\epsilon''$) of Eq. (1) calculated according to the thickness and interpolation curves of the measured complex permittivity of composites with three different concentration of CNFs at $f = 10$ GHz. It was observed that optimum concentrations of $\text{Co}_{(p)}$ and CNFs are 50wt% and 1.8wt%, respectively. The matching thickness of EM wave absorber is 1.8mm.

Fig. 9. Cole-Cole plot of the complex permittivity from the solution of Eq. (1) and from experimental values at $f = 10$ GHz

Fig. 10 shows the reflection loss values of thin EM wave absorbers in X-band. Calculated 10 dB bandwidth of EM wave absorber is about 3 GHz. This results show that EM wave absorber can be thinner and greater maximum reflection loss than previous absorbers [2].

4 Conclusion

This research focused on the design, fabrication, and performance evaluation of EM wave absorbers with dielectric and magnetic lossy materials. Fabrication process was optimized through the observation of the EM property of various composites of different mixing process. Complex permittivity and permeability of the composites were measured from 0.5 GHz to 18 GHz. Optimum roll gap and number of repetition are $10\mu\text{m}$ and 4 cycles, respectively. Design of thin EM wave absorber is designed using Cole-Cole plot and calculation of reflection loss. The calculated thickness, maximum reflection loss and bandwidth of EM wave absorber containing 50wt% $\text{Co}_{(p)}$ and 1.8wt% CNFs is 1.8mm, 45dB and 3GHz, respectively.

Fig. 10. Calculated reflection loss of designed EM wave absorber

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